

SPECIFICITIES OF NONSUICIDAL SELF-HARMING BEHAVIOR AMONG PEERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10697994>

Abstract. *This article discusses the results of the study, which help to find out of specificities of non-suicidal self-harming behavior among adolescents of pre-conscription age. The found results help us to determine at early stages the suitability for military duty of adolescents of pre-conscription age taking into account premorbid features of personality.*

Keywords: *non-suicidal self-harming behavior; peers; personal specificities, military duty.*

Introduction: Each adolescent age is characterized by individual psychological, physiological specificities of personality. We would like to draw attention to the psychological portrait of the personality of teenager with non-suicidal self-harming tendency, since this problem deserves special discussion due to the frequency and complexity of conflicts that arise last ten years.

It is associated not only with the beginning of an acceleration in the rate of physical development, puberty, hormonal changes in the body, and this, in turn, leads to emotional instability. Along with this adolescent's period is associated with an increased desire for self-expression, which most often represented through the great need in special attention in family and among peers. Because of this, conflicts with parents often arise. The problem is especially important in adolescence, since through identification and comparison with others, the peer's self-esteem is formed, a certain ideal is created, discrepancy with which becomes the cause of various conflicts [2, 6].

In adolescence, the productivity of mental activity decreases due to the fact that a change in the type of thinking occurs: the concrete is replaced by the logical.

As a rule, the mental activity of adolescents is directed to the area that is more sensitive that interests them at the moment. Educational activities and school are gradually moving away in the background, the leading activity becomes communicative, that is, intimate and personal communication with peers.

Very often at this time control on the part of parents is weakened: they believe that their child is old enough to solve problems independently and take responsibility for their actions. It is very important to choose the optimal form of help: without hurting the teenager's self-esteem, provide him with timely support [1, 9].

A very important new development of adolescence is the feeling of adulthood. Of course, there is no talk of real adulthood yet, but the teenager strives for identification by yourself with an adult. This is due to the development of physical parameters, psychological maturation, as well as the desire for recognition in society. Often children begin imitate adults, adopt their behavior patterns and habits. This is where they appear attributes of "pseudo-adulthood": smoking cigarettes, hanging out in parks or other places outside of home, etc.

In an effort to gain recognition in the adult world, a teenager begins to engage in activities that are of social benefit and receive public assessment. Psychologically, the teenager has already

formed a need for awareness not only their duties, but also their rights in society. During this period, it is necessary to give the opportunity to satisfy the desire for self-realization, that is, to select for the teenager such a type of activity that, on the one hand, would meet the needs of himself, and on the other hand the other would have a socially useful value. It is noteworthy that this kind of activities can be rewarded and encouraged financially, but in this case, parents or teachers need to think through ways to organize a reward system [2].

To prepare a teenager to face obstacles in adult life, it is necessary to create similar situations already during the difficult period of growing up. Useful occasionally prohibit something. This ability to independently overcome obstacles will contribute to the development of the child as an individual. When parents raise a child, isolating him from the realities of modern life, solving all his problems for him, they are depriving him of the opportunity to gain his own life experience, to find his own way of development [4, 7].

Teachers and parents must support children's self-confidence and their abilities.

The child needs to realize that he is the reason for his successes and failures, ups and downs, that he has the power to achieve something in life. Knowing the age characteristics of students gives the teacher the opportunity to understand what way of interaction with students will be more appropriate in a given situation, which will help lead to an effective resolution of conflict [11, 9].

Early detection of suicidal tendencies and equivalent auto-aggressive and destructive actions, prevention of the risk of developing suicidal behavior are the main tasks of child and adolescent psychiatry [3]. The relevance of the problem of studying specificities of self-harming behavior is caused by the increase in the number of suicides and suicide attempts among children and adolescents as a result of the negative influence of the media and the virtual space of the cybernetic network of the Internet, highlighting suicide as an example to follow and worship [1]. The reaction of parents, the style of family leadership and education can be important factors that predetermine a child's antisocial behavior in the family and society [2]. The behavior of peers is characterized by a high frequency of onsets of depressive states that may be accompanied with ideas of physical disability and one's own humiliation [4]. The rapid growth of suicidal activity, including the facts of auto-aggression among peers for last decades focuses in this issue among a wide range of local and foreign specialists [3,6,7].

The study, conducted on the basis of adolescent departments of the city clinical hospital of Tashkent, set as its goal identifying ways of non-suicidal self-harming behavior in conflict situations. Achieving the goal required problem solving:

- identification of forms of behavior in conflict situations among peers;
- determine the degree of conflict in a given group of peers;
- determine the ratio of constructive and destructive forms of behavior in conflict.

For the study, the method of ascertaining experiment was used, which made it possible to determine the specificities non-suicidal self-harming behavior in conflict in this group of peers. The method of open external observation and conversation with the parents of the given group of peers was used to obtain necessary information and clarification of insufficiently clear details. Statistical data processing methods were used to establish quantitative relationships between the phenomena being studied, and inductive and deductive methods - when generalizing empirically obtained data.

Aim of research: to study the specificities of personal characteristics of peers and self-harming behavior in the micro- and macrosocial mediums.

Material and methods: there were researched 61 peers aged 15 -17 years old, who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the adolescent departments of the city clinical hospital of Tashkent with behavioral disorders and adaptation disorders and with the presence of self-destructive tendencies. All established diagnoses were based on the criteria of the International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision (ICD-10). We identified the personal characteristics of adolescents (PCA) using the Modified Pathocharacterological Diagnostic Questionnaire (MDPO Lichko A.E., Ivanov N.Ya. 2001).

Results and discussion: The analysis revealed the specificities of behavioral disorders in a conflict for an individual personality – one when all five tactics of personality behavior are used, and each of them have a value in the range from 5 to 7 points. If the result is different from the optimal one, then some tactics are weakly expressed - they have a value below 5 points, others - strongly: above 7 points.

As a result of applying MDPO methodology for determining the style of behavior in a conflict situation, the following data were obtained:

▲ Most teenagers (39%) when a conflict situation arises, strive to come to a compromise, make concessions, without losing anything, but without winning anything.

25% adhere to the strategy of competition: these students strive to insist on their own and actively defend their position. They see only two possible ways out of the situation: victory or defeat. 18% of teenagers strive to adapt to the current situation (sacrifice their interests to the interests of others). They strive to save friendly relations with a partner, smooth out all the “sharp corners”, ready to give in, agree with the claims and demands of the partner. About 10% do not adhere to a specific type of behavior in conflict: they strive to reach cooperation or compromise, but these teenagers, along with such forms of behavior, exhibit a desire to adapt. They try to fully reach an agreement, satisfying interests of all parties, but may remain silent about part of their claims in order to maintain friendly relations. This strategy can be considered the most rational. 7% adopt an avoidance strategy, that is, they do not strive both for cooperation and to achieve their own goals: these students take a third-party position and do not insist on their own, do not strive for discussion, refrain from objecting to the opponent and even expressing your position.

▲ From observations of the given group of peers, we can conclude that conflicts are not uncommon in this group. The fact is that there is a “problem” for a teenager in the educative institutes and many students strive to take it. From the research data it is clear that 24% of students - almost a quarter of the class - strive for competition, 15% adapt, then are the subject of activity for potential leaders. Therefore, while adapters will not decide which leader to give their preference, section spheres of influence will not stop.

▲ In addition, observations have shown that there is a serious conflict between boys and girls for instance of unrequired love to the opposite gender. Representatives of the both genders complain about impolite, unfriendly attitude on the part of each other’s. Another wave of conflict flared up inside of families between parents and teenagers. The parents have a certain of model of their child’s behavior, and they transferred it on the child, which may be absolutely different one. All responsibility for resolving intrafamily conflicts lies with their parents.

At the initial stage of our research, we studied the nature of conflict situations that at high risk of developing non-suicidal self-harming behavior, facts of aggression and destructive

tendencies. Identification of the causes of suicidal conflict was carried out according to the classification of Ambrumov A.G., Tikhonenko V.A., according to which the risk of developing suicidal activity in the form of suicide attempts is based on a conflict caused by microsocial factors (family and parenting styles) and macrosocial factors (interpersonal relationships with peers, teachers, people of the opposite gender). A detailed study of the nature of the causes of conflicts among peers with self-harming behavior revealed that they were based on real facts and played a significant role in the life of adolescents. In the first place in terms of frequency of occurrence of the causes of the formation of auto-aggressive tendencies are intra-family conflicts - at 42 (68.85%) peers. The survey revealed that in 16 (26.22%) peers, the cause of family conflict was sibling rivalry as a result of jealousy towards younger brothers and sisters and a variant of the parenting style of emotional rejection. Incorrect type of parental upbringing of the “stick or carrot” type, abuse of a child using physical violence as the cause of the formation of auto-aggressive tendencies was identified in 12 (19.67%) of the examined peers. Living in a dysfunctional family with financial problems was identified in 20 (32.78%) peers. In 13 (21.31%) respondents, the cause of family conflict was the negative attitude of parents towards episodic alcoholism of adolescents, early addiction to smoking cigarettes, and rejection of friendship with people of the opposite gender. Conflicts in interpersonal relationships at the macrosocial level occurred in 19 (31.14%) of the surveyed, among which 9 (14.75%) peers had problems in educational institution (in the form of bullying and didactogeny), 6 (9.83%) teenagers - as a result of conflicts with people of the opposite gender based on unrequited love. In 4 (6.55%) of the examined peers, the main conflict was combined with the effect of additional psychogenies (death of a pet, loss of a football team, car theft, loss of loved ones). Intragroup analysis of the causes of conflicts indicates the predominance of intrafamily nature of conflicts among patients in the study group (Table 1).

Table 1

Specificities of non-suicidal self-harming behavior among peers.

Reasons of conflicts	n=61	%
Intrafamily conflicts	42	68,9
Conflicts in educational institution	9	14,8
Conflicts with people of the opposite gender due to unrequited love	6	9,8
Impact of additional psychogenies	4	6,6
Total	61	100

At the next stage of the study, we identified the premorbid personality specificities of peers with auto-aggressive actions using the MPDO A.E. Lichko (Fig. 1) As we can see according to Figure 1, in the examined group of adolescents, hysteroid (41.0%), epileptoid (26.2%) and cycloid (19.7%) types of character accentuation were more often observed, and sensitive, unstable, psychasthenic and hyperthymic types of character accentuation.

We carried out an intragroup distribution of the causes of conflicts, taking into account the premorbid personality characteristics of peers.

Figure 1. Types of specificities of the examined personality.

Analyzing the results of the distribution of the causes of conflicts, taking into account the personal characteristics of peers, we identified that patients with hysteroid, epileptoid and cycloid character accentuations have high rates of the parameter - intrafamily conflicts, and in patients with labile and psychasthenic personality specificities, conflicts were mainly observed in educational institutions and persons of the opposite gender on the basis of unrequited love (Fig. 2).

Fig .2 Research of conflict situation specificities according to personality of the examined

An analysis of the causes of conflicts, taking into account the personal specificities of peers prone to auto-aggressive self-harming tendencies, indicates the predominance of intra-family conflicts in patients with hysteroid, epileptoid and cycloid personality specificities, which allows them to be classified as a risk group for the potential development of suicidal behavior.

Conclusion: thus, summarizing the research results, it can be assumed that an unfavorable microclimate in the family, facts of psychological and physical violence, the presence of hysteroid, cycloid and epileptoid personality accentuations in adolescents contributed to the risk of developing self-destructive tendencies in the form of self-harming non-suicidal behavior.

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